

MODERN SOLUTIONS TO THE ORIGIN AND PREVENTION OF STABLE ANGINA
PECTORIS

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Abstract. For many years, coronary heart disease (CHD) has been the main cause of death in many economically developed countries, including Uzbekistan. New diagnostic technologies and improvements in the prognostic assessment of patients, along with the ever-evolving evidence base for different treatment strategies, require regular review and updating of existing recommendations.

Key words: Angina, tension angina, stable angina.

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПУТИ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ
СТАБИЛЬНОЙ СТЕНОКАРДИИ.

Аннотация. На протяжении многих лет ишемическая болезнь сердца (ИБС) является основной причиной смертности во многих экономически развитых странах, в том числе в Узбекистане. Новые диагностические технологии и улучшения в прогностической оценке пациентов, а также постоянно развивающаяся доказательная база для различных стратегий лечения требуют регулярного пересмотра и обновления существующих рекомендаций.

Ключевые слова: Стенокардия, стенокардия напряжения, стабильная стенокардия.

Complications: The most commonly diagnosed form of coronary artery disease is stable angina. Stable angina is a clinical syndrome characterized by chest discomfort that occurs during physical exertion or emotional stress. The attack occurs at the same load level and passes within 1-5 minutes. after termination.

Purpose of study: Patients with stable angina are considered to have a relatively good prognosis. In clinical trials of antianginal and prophylactic therapy and/or revascularization, the annual mortality rate is 1.2-2.4% per year [1-6], the annual rate of cardiac death is 0.6-1.4% and death between non-lim myocardial infarction (MI). 0.6% in the RITA-2 (Second Randomized

Interventional Treatment of Angina) trial [4] and 2.7% in the COURAGE (Clinical Outcomes Using Revascularization and Aggressive Drug Evaluation) [1] trial.

However, the individual prognosis of a particular patient with stable angina can vary significantly depending on his main clinical, functional and anatomical features.

Research results: This is shown in data from the REACH (Reducing Atherothrombosis for Sustainable Health) [7] registry: the annual mortality rate in high-risk patients with peripheral arterial disease, post-infarction atherosclerosis and diabetes mellitus (DM) is 3.8% formed, and in low-risk patients it was 3.8%.

Prognostic assessment is an important part of the diagnosis of stable angina. On the one hand, there is a need to identify patients with more severe disease whose outcomes may be improved by more aggressive treatment, including revascularization. On the other hand, it is also important to identify patients with less severe disease and better prognosis, thereby avoiding unnecessary aggressive tests and revascularization procedures.

The prognosis is determined by several factors:

1. Coronary reserve, i.e. increased work of the left ventricle and the possibility of sufficient increase in coronary blood flow with the amount of myocardium with insufficient blood supply. In conditions of energy starvation, the contractility of the myocardium can be significantly reduced, which leads to ischemia of a large part of the left ventricle or a small heart failure, but this is enough to reduce the function of the pump and increase the existing contractility disorders. previous myocardial injury.

2. risk factors that accelerate the development of atherosclerosis and the formation of unstable plaque, the sudden rupture of atheromatous plaque responsible for the development of unstable angina and acute coronary events are not related to the severity of pre-existing stenosis.

According to the 2013 ESC guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of stable angina, once stable CAD is diagnosed and optimal medical therapy (OMT) is initiated, coronary risk stratification is performed based on invasive tests that are not usually available. selection of patients who may benefit from revascularization. Depending on the severity of symptoms, early coronary angiography can be performed with appropriate confirmation of the importance of stenoses and subsequent revascularization, bypassing noninvasive tests. Revascularization confers a clear prognostic benefit only in high-risk patients and provides little or no improvement in prognosis in those who already have a good prognosis.

Previously, in the ESC recommendations [8], an annual risk of cardiac death greater than 2% was considered the recommended threshold for revascularization. The 2013 guidelines [9]

revised the severity of angina pectoris, suggesting that surgical treatment significantly improves the prognosis compared to medical treatment and that high-risk patients should be considered those with a risk of cardiac death greater than 3% per year did

Summary: Duke treadmill index = exercise time in minutes - 5 × ST deviation in mm - 4 × angina index (angina index: 0 - angina was absent, 1 - angina appeared, 2 - angina to stop the test caused).

An approximate assessment of the risk of myocardial infarction and death using the Duke treadmill index (Table 2) helps to choose the next tactics of patient management:

For low-risk patients, further stress imaging and coronary angiography are considered inappropriate, and drug therapy is recommended;

For moderate-risk patients, stress imaging is recommended (Table 2), myocardial perfusion with normal or normal heart size during exercise is a favorable prognostic marker, and drug treatment is recommended for them. will be done. in patients and in the presence of left ventricular dysfunction - revascularization [10, 11].

The recommendations of the EOC suggest some changes in the tactics of drug treatment of stable angina:

It is recommended to start prevention of attacks by prescribing β -blockers and/or calcium channel blockers;

as second-line drugs, it is recommended to add long-acting nitrates, ivabradine, nicorandil, or ranolazine according to heart rate, blood pressure, and drug tolerance;

Trimetazidine may also be considered as a second-line treatment;

in certain patients, depending on the level of comorbidity / tolerance, second-line drugs can be used as first-line drugs;

β -blockers should be considered first in asymptomatic patients with a large ischemic area (>10%).

β -Blockers (BABs) are effective antianginal agents that relieve symptoms, increase exercise tolerance, and reduce the consumption of short-acting nitrates [12]. They reduce the need for oxygen by reducing heart rate, blood pressure and myocardial contractility. Perfusion of ischemic areas is improved by prolonging diastole (ie, perfusion time) and eliminating coronary steal due to increased vascular resistance in non-ischemic areas.

Commonly used β 1-blockers with proven high antianginal efficacy are metoprolol, atenolol, and bisoprolol. To achieve an antianginal effect during the day, β 1-blockers with long-term blood circulation in the plasma (for example, bisoprolol) or dosage forms that maintain the

plasma concentration of the drug (for example, metoprolol CR) are prescribed. To maintain the same concentration of atenolol in the plasma (half-life 6-9 hours), dosing twice a day is acceptable, but it should be remembered that the duration of the β -blocking effect increases with the increase in the dose of the drug. . The effect of beta-blockers in stable angina can be considered only if their use achieves a clear effect of beta-adrenergic receptor blockade. To do this, it is necessary to keep the heart rate at rest in the range of 55-60 beats / min. More precisely, the degree of blockade of β -adrenergic receptors achieved can be evaluated by an exercise test [8].

A meta-analysis examining the effect of various beta-blockers on mortality showed a significant reduction in mortality with long-term use after myocardial infarction. Based on these data, it has been suggested that beta-blockers may also have a cardioprotective effect in patients with stable coronary disease. However, this was not proven in a placebo-controlled trial [13].

Large studies on the effectiveness of beta-blockers for stable angina - APIS [14] and TIBET [15] - did not show a significant difference in results between patients treated with beta blockers or calcium channel blockers, nifedipine or verapamil. These studies confirmed the beneficial antianginal properties of β -blockers, but did not answer whether treatment changes the prognosis of patients with stable angina.

REFERENCES

1. Farrukh S. ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. Special Issue 8. – C. 493-499.
2. Sarkisova, V., Lapasova, Z., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). O. Rakhmanov INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE PELVIC WOMEN ORGANS.
3. Shernazarov I., Shernazarov F. Problems of translation of features related to the way of life of peoples //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. B1. – C. 80-83.
4. Jalalova, D., Axmedov, A., Kuryazov, A., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). COMBINED DENTAL AND EYE PATHOLOGY. Science and innovation, 1(8), 91-100.
5. Shernazarov F., Zuhridinovna J. D. Microcirculation disorders in the vascular system of the bulbar conjunctiva in the initial manifestations of cerebral blood supply deficiency //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. Special Issue 2. – C. 515-522.
6. Solovyova, Y., Prostyakova, N., Sharapova, D., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). The relevance of psychotic disorders in the acute period of a stroke. Science and innovation, 2(D12), 212-217.

7. Rotanov, A., Karshiyev, Z., Sharapova, D., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution. *Science and innovation*, 2(D11), 309-315.
8. Shernazarov F. COMBINED DENTAL AND EYE PATHOLOGY //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 91-100.
9. Madaminov M., Shernazarov F. Breast cancer detection methods, symptoms, causes, treatment //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 530-535.
10. Jalalova, D., Axmedov, A., Kuryazov, A., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). СОЧЕТАННАЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ И ГЛАЗНАЯ ПАТОЛОГИЯ. *Science and innovation*, 1(D8), 91-100.
11. Prostyakova, N., Solovyova, Y., Sharapova, D., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia. *Science and innovation*, 2(D12), 158-165.
12. Jalalova D., Raxmonov X., Shernazarov F. РОЛЬ С-РЕАКТИВНОГО БЕЛКА В ПАТОГЕНЕЗЕ СОСУДИСТЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ОРГАНА ЗРЕНИЯ У БОЛЬНЫХ АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТЕНЗИЕЙ //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 114-121.
13. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 186-191.
14. Sedenkova M. et al. The possibility of predicting the time of formation and development of alcohol dependence: the role of genetic risk, family weight and its level //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 173-178.
15. Shamilov V. et al. Disorders of decision-making in the case of depression: clinical evaluation and correlation with eeg indicators //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 198-204.
16. Uskov A. et al. Modern methods of therapeutic fasting as a way to overcome the pharmaco-resistance of mental pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 179-185.
17. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular disease isomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 166-172.
18. Tahirova, J., Roziklov, N., Mamatkulova, F., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). Insomnia problem causes of sleep disorder, help measures at home. *Science and innovation*, 1(D8), 521-525.

19. Qizi T. J. I., Farrukh S. Treatment of myocardial infarction and first aid //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. D3. – C. 317-320.
20. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.
21. Abdurakhmanov I., Shernazarov F. SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D10. – C. 164-168.
22. Tahirova J. et al. Neurose causes and mechanisms of development, symptoms, treatment, prevention //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. D8. – C. 515-520.
23. Tahirova J., Shernazarov F. Symptoms of hymoritis, treatment, methods of folk medicine, prevention //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. D8. – C. 983-990.
24. Shodiyeva D., Shernazarov F. Analysis of the compounds providing antihelmitic effects of chichorium intybus through fractionation. Science and innovation, 2 (D2), 64-70. – 2023.
25. Jalalova D., Normatova N., Shernazarov F. Genetic markers for the development of diabetic retinopathy //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 8. – C. 919-923.
26. Abdukodirova S., Shernazarov F. SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS AND TREATMENT OF ACUTE OBSTRUCTIVE BRONCHITIS IN CHILDREN OF EARLY AGE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 5-8.

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